

THE SOCIO-ECONOMIC EFFECT OF TERRORISM IN NIGERIA

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Abstract

This study investigates the socio-economic impact of terrorism in Nigeria. Terrorism is a worldwide phenomenon confronting all states in the international system. The attacks perpetrated by the sect have resulted in the loss of thousands of lives and properties worth billions of naira. In investigating the socio-economic impact of terrorism in Nigeria, the study employs the qualitative approach and utilises the case study research design. The study retrieves data from secondary sources including books, book chapters, journal articles, and newspapers. To analyse the data retrieved, the study adopts thematic analysis to segment the data retrieved into themes in accordance with the objective of the study. Findings of the study reveal that terrorism in Nigeria particularly the activities of the Boko Haram sect have stalled education in affected areas, resulted in large numbers of deaths and the destruction of infrastructure and livelihood of affected individuals. The study recommends that security should be reinforced through the presence of military to deter the resurrection of the terrorist sect when it has been defeated and the government should seek collaboration with organisations in the private sector to rebuild affected areas.

Résumé

Cette étude examine les impacts socio-économiques du terrorisme au Nigéria. Le terrorisme est un phénomène mondial auquel sont confrontés tous les États du système international. Les attaques perpétrées par la secte ont entraîné la perte de milliers de vies et de propriétés valant des milliards. Pour interroger sur les impacts socio-économiques du terrorisme au Nigéria, l'étude utilise l'approche qualitative et la conception de l'étude de cas. L'étude récupère des données à partir de sources secondaires, notamment des livres, des chapitres de livres, des articles de revues et des journaux. Pour analyser les données récupérées, l'étude adopte une analyse thématique pour segmenter les données en thèmes conformément à l'objectif de l'étude. Les conclusions de l'étude révèlent que le terrorisme au Nigéria, en particulier les activités de la secte Boko Haram, a paralysé l'éducation dans les zones touchées avec un grand nombre de morts et la destruction des infrastructures et des moyens de subsistance de la population. L'étude recommande que la sécurité soit renforcée par la présence d'armées pour

dissuader la résurrection de la secte terroriste après sa défaite et la collaboration du gouvernement avec des organisations du secteur privé pour reconstruire les zones touchées.

Mots clés: Terrorisme, terrorisme religieux, Boko Haram, effet socio-économique

Introduction

Terrorism is a worldwide phenomenon confronting all states in the international system. Beginning with the 9/11 attacks in New York and Washington in the United States of America in September 2001, terrorism has evolved into employing different means to ensuring the vast destruction of lives and properties (Ilardi, 2009). According to Vision of Humanity (2017: p. 24) at least 106 (one hundred and six countries) of the world have encountered one terrorist activity or the other. Nigeria is not excluded from this as the country is plagued with activities of one of the deadliest terrorist sects in the world. The Boko Haram sect has continually perturbed the North Eastern part of the state through armed violence. Poised as a radical Islamic fundamentalist organization, the sect stands at the fore-front of the campaign against western or formal education in Nigeria. As the English translation of its name goes; western education is sin, the terrorist sect has challenged institutions of government and of learning in the Eastern region of the country. These actions have most times resulted in mass amounts of deaths and destruction of properties (Imhonopi & Urim, 2016).

As a result, the Nigerian Government through the country's Armed Forces has engaged in diverse operations to curb the activities of the terrorist sect. Such operations include operation Lafiya Dole, Operation Zaman Lafiya and a host of others (Ibrahim & Bala, 2018). This has culminated in a protracted war between the country's military forces and the sect. Despite this, Boko Haram's activities have spilled from inside Nigeria into neighbouring countries including Niger, Cameroon and Chad (International Crisis Group, 2017).

Numerous studies have been conducted on Boko Haram's terrorist activities. Walker (2012) focused on the activities of the terrorist sect in Nigeria, its fundamental ideologies and outlined attack patterns. Brechenmacher (2019) examined the paths to reconstructing the North Eastern Region of Nigeria following the defeat of the sect. Dunn (2018) examined the impact of Boko Haram on childhood development in Nigeria. Despite the plethora of studies that subsist on the subject matter, no study has adequately investigated and outlined the socio-economic implications of the Boko Haram terrorist sect on Nigeria. Thus, the objective of this paper is to investigate the socio-economic implications of terrorism in Nigeria.

The Concept of Terrorism

Terrorism is a worldwide phenomenon confronting all states in the international system. In fact, Rapoport (2017), states that “it is a global phenomenon that involves the use of terror for a wide range of purposes. With respect to its meaning, a plethora of definitions exist, thereby offering varying perspectives on the subject matter”. This is as a result of the understanding of the concept by scholars, statesmen, etc. In other words, numerous definitions of the concept abound (Krieger & Meiericks, 2011). According to Schinkel (2009) (p.179), terrorism involves “the premeditated and systematic use of violence against a group of people to instil fear”. For Kydd & Walter (2006), terrorism refers to the process of exerting or perpetrating acts of violence against civilian targets for the achievement of a definite goal. Terrorism is usually construed as a crime. However, this definition does not present a holistic perspective of the concept as it does not only involve violence, but the selective use of the same. In congruence, Fletcher (2006) (p. 12) points out “that there is a better way to think of terrorism than just crime”. Terrorism and terrorist organisations mobilize resources both human and otherwise to carry out their activities. The second approach is political opportunities. “Terrorism is enabled by certain external factors. Chief among this is external political climates” (Okpadah, 2017, p. 47). Despite its prominence in the 21st century, terrorism is not of a recent development as it has its roots in history. The first record of the organised and systematic use of violence can be traced back to the activities of the zealots in first century Palestine (Chaliand & Blin, 2007). Zealotry was a Jewish national liberation movement which through revolution sought to emancipate Jerusalem from the grip of Roman governance and domination. In action, the zealots used violence and coercion to achieve their goals which among others included opposing Roman domination (Aslan, 2014). Aside the zealot, another group that laid the historical foundations for the concept of terrorism was the Assassins. The Assassins, also known as the Order of Assassins (Hashashiyah) used violence for political, social and religious gains. While existent in Syria and Iran, the assassins targeted high profile individuals and killed them. The purpose of this was to instil fear in the minds of people in their societies. For the Assassins, the primary objective of the use of violence was to regain the power of the state (Chaliand & Blin, 2007). By so doing, the Assassins introduced the systematic use of violence into the phenomenon of terrorism.

Waves of Terrorism

The origin and the development of terrorism can be discussed in waves. According to Rapoport (2013) (p. 34) “there are four distinctive waves of terrorism, all of which existed at one point or the other between 1800 and the 21st century”. For Rapoport (2002) (p. 36), the first wave which is the first expression

of modern terrorism was in the 1800s. Described as the anarchist wave, it involved the creation of a doctrine. Such terrorist acts involved the creation of propaganda by deed rather than extensive speeches. This idea of terrorism is built on the existence of hostilities, moral conventions to muffle these which generate guilt. These moral conventions are creations of historical accounts. As such, they are over time, confronted by the terrorist, who employs violence as an instrument to instil fear and achieve political, social and/ or economic goals (Rapoport, 2002). These featured in Vera Zasulich's shooting of a police commander in St. Petersburg, Russia in 1878, which marked the first modern terrorist act (Kaplan, 2016). "The acts of terrorism in this wave resulted in slow but steady political reforms and the declining legitimacies of monarchies" (Rapoport, 2004 cited in Walls, 2017, p. 56).

The second wave of terrorism was the anti-colonial wave, which developed following the conclusion of World War I (WWI) (Jach-Chrzaszaz, 2017). The international power structure of the period necessitated the development of this wave, as European countries were colonial masters of African, Middle Eastern and Asian countries. However, victors of WWI employed the principle of national self determination to break up the existing imperialist empires. Territories that were not sufficiently developed for independence were subsumed under the League of Nations mandates. "As such, these countries were to be administered by the victorious countries in the war" (Walls, 2017). Terrorist campaigns were waged in such territories, which had existing divisions concerning governance and the presence of colonial powers. An instance of this is the tensions between Arab and Jewish populations in Palestine (Walls, 2017).

The third wave of terrorism is denoted as the New Left Wave which began in the 1960s. According to Jach-Chrzaszaz (2017: p. 101), "the third wave of terrorism was marked by the development of leftist concepts and ideologies as developed by prevalent terrorist groups of the time". Worthy of note is the fact that this was the cold war era. Hence, the rivalry between the United States of America (U.S.A.) and the Union of Soviet Socialist Republics (USSR) promoted the creation of these leftist ideologies and also the terrorist groups that created them. Jach-Chrzaszaz (2017) points out that the Central Intelligence Agency (CIA) supported the creation of military groups designed to oppose communist movements in Italy. These culminated in terrorist attacks in the country in the 1970s (Jach-Chrzaszaz, 2017).

The fourth wave is the current expression of terrorism in the world. It is described as religious wave which came into existence in the latter part of the 1970s. Terrorist acts were motivated by religious doctrines and principles as opposed to ideologies, colonial tensions, etc (Walls, 2017). The emergence of the religious

wave was necessitated by three major events in the international system namely: the Iranian Revolution, the dawn of the new Islamic Century and the Soviet Union's invasion of Afghanistan (Walls, 2017). While Islam has played a salient role in this wave of terrorism, it is also important to make mention of Jewish and Christian terrorist activities namely the Jewish attempts to blow up Islam's sacred shrines in Jerusalem and assassination campaigns against Palestinian Mayors. Although Christian terrorist attacks have been minimal, they are evident. An instance is the Oklahoma City bombing of 1995 (Rapoport, 2002).

Terrorism in Nigeria

Nigeria has not been excluded from the list of countries confronting terrorist groups and their activities. Africa's most populous black country has been confronting the scourge of terrorism since 2009 as perpetrated by the Boko Haram sect. As such it will be difficult to describe the Nigerian experience of terrorism without paying allusions to the Boko Haram Sect. The term "boko haram" is the result of a confluence between two distinct languages. "Boko" is Hausa word for "book" and "Haram" is the Arabic translation for "forbidden" or "sinful". These terms translate to the message championed by the sect, "western education is sin" (Uzodike & Maiangwa, 2012). Boko Haram is an Islamic fundamentalist group which was founded in 2009 by Mohammed Yusuf. In its early days, the group was not a terrorist sect but rather marked a disagreement with the Islamic and political doctrines and configurations of Borno, Nigeria. As a result, Yusuf as the leader and his followers withdrew to found and operate their own religious beliefs. The group however began violent activities when it assassinated ShekhJa'afarMahmood Adam, a popular teacher and preacher at the Ndimi Mosque in Maiduguri and declared war against the state. This forced the government of the day to crackdown on the group which summarily resulted in the death of the group's leader Mohammed Yusuf (Walker, 2012).

With the death of Yusuf and arrest of some of its members, the group became violent and began a series of assassinations and killings in Maiduguri, targeting police checkpoints, and traditional leaders who aided police with information leading to the arrest of its members, etc. By December 2010, the group had employed the use of bombs and explosives which increased the amount of people killed per time. Many attacks as perpetrated by the sect during this period employed such weapons and targeted soft spots, especially areas with dense civilian population. Notable attacks among these include the Christmas Eve 2010 attacks in Jos where churches and markets were bombed, the bombing of the market inside the grounds of the Mogadishu barracks which killed ten and a host of numerous attacks (Walker, 2012). Over the years, Boko Haram became more aggressive and violent, holding public executions, embarking on sporadic

shootings in communities. Notable among their attacks is the kidnap of 329 girls from a boarding school in Chibok (Guitta & Simcox, 2014). Also, due to “the attacks of the Boko Haram sect, over 100,000 people have been killed since May of 2011, along with more than 244,000 Nigerians seeking refuge in neighbouring countries” (CFR, 2020, p. 2). This caused outcry and protests from international organisations and notable figures in the world. The Boko Haram sect also spread its activities to other regions and states of West Africa. Countries of the Lake Chad Basin, Nigeria, Niger, Chad and Cameroon have suffered from the pervasive attacks of the terrorist sect (International Crisis Group, 2017).

In response to the sect, the Nigerian government, through its Armed Forces has embarked on a protracted war in the Northern part of the country. The Nigerian military has been deployed in the North Eastern part of the country to battle the terrorist sect. A series of operations have been embarked on by the country’s armed forces notable among which is Operation Lafiya Dole (Ibrahim & Bala, 2018). Operation Lafiya Dole was put in place by the Nigerian military following the failure of Operation Zaman Lafiya. The operation was enacted to confront and weaken the Boko Haram. The operation had its command centre in Maiduguri under the leadership of Lt. Gen. Tukur Buratai, the then Chief of Army Staff (Ewa, 2018). Other efforts by countries in the Lake Chad Basin includes “the Civilian Joint Task Force (CJTF) which is a militia set up to protect civilian communities against the terrorist sect” (Ibrahim & Bala, 2018).

Boko Haram and the Fourth Wave of Religious Terrorism

The narrative of Boko Haram’s terrorist activities in Nigeria coincides with the attributes of the fourth wave. The religious foundations of the Boko Haram insurgency synchronize with the precepts of traditional Islam, one of the many variants of radical Islam (Agbibo, 2013). Radical Islam views Islam as a historical, political, economic and socio-cultural religion of change and revolution. For Radical Muslims, Islam is a state and an ideology by which a state should govern. Muslims in this case feel and shoulder the burden to transform a state from secular to Islam oriented (Hassan, 2015). Similarly, Esposito (2015) posits that Radical Islam believers and extremists cite the records of violence in the Quran and use it to justify the battle against a secular state. As such, the battle/ rebellion against a secular state are branded a holy war (Jihad) by extremists’ groups.

The linkage between Radical Islam and violence is manifested through the hatred of secular states by believers. Agbibo (2013) (p. 67) explains “that radical Islam groups, in their hatred of secular governments, states and cultures, dream and envision revolutionary changes that would replace such cultures with godly social

orders along the tenets of Islam”. Hence, religious extremists capitalise on scriptures such as in Quran 2:191 which says “and slay them wherever ye find them, and drive them out of the places whence they drove you out, for persecution is worse than slaughter... and fight them until fitnah is no more, and religion is for Allah”.

The Boko Haram sect uses the above as its ideological base. It conceives western culture as contrary to the teachings of the Prophet and as such, employs the precepts of Islam through violence to propagate the teachings of the Prophet. This is reflected in the name members, brand themselves: *Jama'atulAlhulSunnahLidda'watiwal Jihad* which in English is translated to mean People Committed to the Propagation of the Prophet's Teachings and Jihad (Agbibo, 2013). The foundations of such an ideology lay with the founder of the sect Mohammed Yusuf. “Yusuf was a young Nigerian born Muslim from Yobe state, who received his Quranic and Islamic education from Niger” (Salaam, 2013). According to Mueller (2016) (p. 95), “Niger has over time witnessed the resurgence of radical Islam which has found expression in deadly attacks on Christians and secularism”. For Salaam (2013: p. 3), “it is believed that Yusuf acquired his ideology on radical Islam there. After returning to Nigeria, Yusuf moved from one group to another until he joined the Ahlulsunnawal'jama'ahhijra also known as Shabaab”. Yusuf rose through the ranks until he became Amir (President) of the group. Upon assuming the mantle of leadership, Yusuf changed the ideological and religious stance of the group to reflect the core tenets of radical Islam which involved intolerance for secular and non-Islamic principles and beliefs (Salaam, 2013). This ideology has been the foundation of the sect's attacks in the North Eastern part of Nigeria.

Factors Responsible for the Advent of the Boko Haram Terrorist Group in Nigeria

Various factors are responsible for the advent of Boko Haram sect in Nigeria. One of such factors is poor governance. Originally, the purpose of governance is to draw out plan and (political, socio-economic and cultural) objectives of a state or province ensure order within the society and prevent uprisings or anarchy (Bourne, 2014). However, the situation of governance witnessed in Boko Haram hotspots before the emergence of the sect differs from this. Poor governance in the region led to the absence of basic amenities and projects and consequently led to an increase in social gaps between the rich and poor and vast infrastructural decay (Suleiman & Karim, 2015).

Furthermore, it is alleged that the sect is the creation of numerous actors in the north. According to Agbibo (2013) (p. 99) the Boko Haram sect was a creation

of politicians, notably governors of northern states, who employed the services of militants to intimidate and score political points against opponents and also gain relevance at the federal level. The sect was promised 5 million naira monthly which was later increased to 10 million naira, to perpetrate acts that will be advantageous to governors but at the same time inimical to the security of the state (Agbiboa, 2013).

Economic factors are also worthy of consideration when discussing the causes of terrorism in Nigeria. For Ukauwa, Celik, Jelilov & Olali (2019), the endemic poverty in Nigeria, compounded with increasing levels of illiteracy are to blame for the development of the terrorist sect. This is visible in the poverty index in which Nigeria ranks as the 158th poorest economy in the world (Kester, 2012 cited in Ukauwa et al, 2019, p. 18).

The Socio-economic Impact of Terrorism in Nigeria

The implications of terrorism in Nigeria are far reaching. This section discusses the socio-economic impact of terrorism in Nigeria. Undoubtedly, the campaign of violence in form of terrorism by the terror sect has resulted in the death of a number of people. The RFI (2019) (p. 13) reports that more than 27,000 people have died as a result of Boko Haram's violence and more continue to die on a daily basis either by the suicide bombing attempts of the group's militants or sporadic shootings. Within the Lake Chad Basin, the death toll tops 150,000 (CFR, 2020, p. 4). An indirect implication of this is that many have lost loved ones and families have lost bread winners. According to Mercy Corps (2016: p. 28), many women have lost their husbands and bread winners to the menace that is Boko Haram. This has plunged some into despair and also forced other women to fill roles they would rather have not occupied. The unabated killings by the sect have also created an atmosphere of fear for many in the North East. Akinyetun (2017) points out that many stay indoors due to the fear of being killed by the terrorists.

Civilian deaths are not the only ones recorded. Numerous soldiers have been killed in the fight against insurgency in the North East. On the 23rd of March 2020, between 50 and 75 soldiers were killed by the terrorist sect. This massacre occurred when troops tried to launch an offensive. Additional 92 Chadian soldiers were killed in the ambush which lasted for several hours (Al Jazeera & News Agencies, 2020). While this constitutes a loss of human resource in the fight against terrorism, many families have lost their loved ones in the conflict. The governor of Borno State, the epicentre of Boko Haram's activities, pointed out that the military must recruit 100,000 soldiers to bring an end to the decade

long fight against terrorism (Olukayode & Clowes, 2020, p. 34). Ultimately this may culminate in more deaths and injuries for military men.

Many in North Eastern Nigeria have been unable to continue their educational pursuits due to the endemic activities of the Boko Haram terrorist group in line with its central ideology; western education is sin, the sect's campaign of violence has kept many away from educational institutions in the region and has also caused many schools and institutions to halt activities (Uzodike & Maiangwa, 2012). Some of the Chibok female students who have been rescued from the clutches of the sect, following their kidnap in April of 2014 have not been able to go back to school. Also, in February 2018, 119 girls from a boarding school in the small town of Dapchi, Yobe state were abducted while preparing for breakfast in their boarding school (Abraak & Maclean, 2018). While the Nigerian government was able to achieve the release of some of the girls kidnapped, they have not been able to go back to school. Adebayo & Busari (2018) record that the girls were warned by the Boko Haram sect not to go back to school. Many parents embraced this warning due to the lack of protection while the girls are in school. While many of the girls returned, one of them was held back for refusing to renounce her faith as a Christian. This led to outcry from different quarters of the world on the persistent captivity of the Leah due to her strong ties to the Christian faith (Agekameh, 2019). Some parents of the returned girls are afraid of and reluctant to send their daughters back to school for the fear of being kidnapped or killed.

The economic implications of Boko Haram's activities in Nigeria are also worthy of consideration. Holistically, Nigeria has spent more than US\$1 Billion in the fight against Boko Haram insurgency (Semeniworima, 2018). This has been spent on procuring numerous military equipment for the armed forces to engage the terrorists in combat. This is aside the budgetary allocation that the Ministry of Defence receives. In 2017 alone, the ministry received 465.5 Billion Naira in budgetary allocation (Duruji, Idowu, Dibia, & Duruji-Moses, 2018, p. 445). When compared with the previous allocations the ministry has received, a constant increase of funds allocated is sighted, largely due to the battle against terrorism. Below is a table detailing the budgetary allocations the ministry of defence has received between 2012 and 2017.

S/N	Year	Amount (Billion Naira)
	2012	332.2
	2013	364.4
	2014	349.7
	2015	375.5
	2016	443.1
	2017	465.5

Source: Duruji et al. (2018)

These are amounts allocated to the Ministry of defence to enable it actively combat the Boko Haram terrorist sect. These amounts constantly swallowed by the fight against terrorism could have been used to fund other pressing development needs

A significant amount of businesses and organisations in the North Eastern part of Nigeria have been forced to close down due to the activities of the terrorist sect. Restaurants and banks are suffering the implications of the sect's activities. Invariably, individuals in affected areas are unable to make earnings meet and have access to their different sources of livelihoods (Dauda, 2014). This is not a representative of other manufacturing industries that have also incurred human, material as well as financial resources as a result of Boko Haram's activities. Trade also suffers heavily from the activities of the Boko Haram terrorist activities as routes linking the North and Southern parts of Nigeria have become generally unsafe. ACAPS (2014) submits that the movement of goods between the north and the south of Nigeria have been disrupted as a result of the security challenge.

Conclusion and Recommendations

This study examined the socio-economic implications of terrorism in Nigeria. Boko Haram is an Islamic fundamentalist group which was founded in 2009 by Mohammed Yusuf. The group has grown to become one of the deadliest terrorist organisations in the world. The attacks have resulted in numerous deaths and the destruction of properties. Education in the region has been stalled and families and individuals have been adversely affected by the activities of the terrorist sect.

In the light of the above findings, this study recommends that the government's repudiation of the social, economic and environmental impacts of the sect's activities will be futile without confronting and defeating the terrorist group. Hence government must adequately defeat the group before it can begin activities towards resolving the adverse effects of the sect. Also, government should collaborate with organisations in the private sector to rebuild the North Eastern region in terms of infrastructure, education and so on. In addition, security should be reinforced through the presence of military and paramilitary forces to deter the resurrection of the terrorist sect when it has been defeated.

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